

Effect of Workplace Bullying and Harassment on Performance of Academic Staff in Olabisi Onabanjo University, Ogun State

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the effect of workplace bullying and harassment on performance of academic staff in Olabisi Onabanjo University (OOU) with the objective of examining the effect of workplace environment on performance of Academic Staff in OOU; examining the effect of leadership style on workplace bullying and harassment of Academic Staff in OOU; exploring the effect of job design on workplace bullying and harassment on performance of Academic Staff in OOU; and investigating the effect of supervisor support on workplace bullying and harassment on performance of Academic Staff in OOU. Theory of Work Adjustment and Two-Factor Theory underpinned the study. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design and a population of six hundred and twenty eight (628) academic staff of OOU, Ogun State where 150 respondents were used as sample size; data were obtained through primary data and analysed using both descriptive and inferential statistics with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) and the data were presented with the frequency distribution table. Findings from the study revealed that all components tested such as workplace environment ($0.847 > 0.5$), leadership style ($0.967 > 0.5$), job design ($0.943 > 0.5$) and supervisor support ($0.844 > 0.5$) all affect and have positive significant relationship with workplace bullying and harassment on performance of Academic Staff in OOU but at varying degrees. The study concluded that workplace bullying is a harmful problem leading high level of turnover and huge decline in performance rate; thus, creating shortage of man power in the Nigerian educational sector in Nigeria. Therefore, reviewing the Human Resources structure, checkmating leadership, workplace environment, job design and supervisor's support and conducting regular training, workshops and seminars to train academic staff in OOU on the effect of workplace bullying to the development of Institution will go a long way in ameliorating this menace.

Keywords: Academic Staff Performance, Workplace Bullying and Harassment, Job Design, Leadership Style, Supervisor's Support.

How to Cite:

INTRODUCTION

Workplace bullying destroys the person in every sense, it not only affects their career but it also puts their health at risk. Workplace culture matters a lot as it has a direct impact on the employee's performance. If the organization culture is healthy, positive, an employee will able to give his/her best in an organization but if the work culture is not sound it will influence his/her performance in an organization and also in his/her family. Namie (2007) states that abusive, insulting language, spreading gossip, rumors harmful or offensive initiation practices, physical assault or unlawful threats, giving too

much workload to the person, setting the timelines for the employee which are difficult to achieve, giving the task that is beyond the ability of a person, continuously ignoring a person at the workplace, and purposely denying access to information that are considered as workplace bullying.

Background

Workplace bullying and harassment is a pattern of persistent, offensive, abusive, intimidating or insulting behavior, abuse of power or unfair punishment which upsets, threatens and humiliates the recipient(s), undermining their self-confidence, reputation and ability to perform (Oghojafor, Muo and Olufayo, 2012). It manifests in a wide variety of behaviors such as, public humiliation and criticism, verbal abuse, social exclusion, intimidation, inaccurate accusations, spreading rumours, ignoring people for long periods and undermining victims' professional status (Markovits et al., 2010).

This is characterized by frequency of incidence, duration and reaction on the side of both the perpetrator and victim, ultimately caused by power struggles in ineffective working environments (Owoyemi and Oyelere, 2010). According to Owoyemi and Sheenam (2011), the negative effects of bullying behavior on an organization include loss of employee morale; a high level of absence from work, depression, anxiety, and physical ailments; decreased productivity and profit; a high level of attrition; loss of customers; a poor reputation in the industry; negative media attention; legal action; and workplace violence. The study will examine the effects of workplace bullying behavior and employee performance.

Employees working in markedly bureaucratic organisations such as Olabisi Onabanjo University with time-consuming policies and procedures, a lack of flexibility, and limited attention toward employee satisfaction are at greatest risk of workplace violence. This study on workplace bullying is significant because workplace bullying is costing employers money and costing employees their health and usually their jobs (Bockerman and Ilmakunnas, 2012). Workplace bullying affects the direct and indirect costs to the organization. Direct costs are easier to identify employee absence, increased turnover, increased legal fees, and increased security expenses (Owoyemi and Oyelere, 2010).

Turnover costs an organization dearly, not only through the loss of industry knowledge, but also in the time and money spent recruiting and training new employees. Work environment harassing is characterized as continuous presentation to negative acts that the objective experiences issues safeguarding him/herself against due to a real or perceived power imbalance between the parties Einarsen, Hoel, Zapf, and Cooper (2011). The past decade bullying has received growing attention in organization research where analysts have announced disturbing discoveries about the negative results related with harassing, both for the people and the associations concerned. Concerning the consequences for the association, tormenting has been appeared to be related with higher turnover and plan to leave the association, higher absenteeism, and decreased commitment and efficiency (Salin, 2003).

Employee performance is basically outcomes accomplished and achievements made at work. Performance refers to keeping up plans while going for the outcomes. Although performance evaluation is the heart of performance management, the performance of an individual or an organization depends heavily on all organizational policies, practices, and design features of an organization (Anitha, 2014). Exposure to bullying in the workplace is not only associated with reduced health and well-being among those being bullied, it is also associated with individual, unit and organizational outcomes related to performance and productivity, negative outcomes for patient care, increased absenteeism, increased turnover intentions and reduced job satisfaction and engagement (Sheehan, McCabe, & Garavan, 2018).

Statement of the Problem

Workplace bullying is widespread and has the potential to have devastating effects on an employee's performance. Employees who are bullied, and those who work with bullies, take sick leave more often than those who are not bullied on the job. Although bullying has become a popular subject of study since the mid-1990s, the relationship between bullying in the workplace and job performance are not well known. The menace of workplace bullying has attracted significant attention in the modernised economies of the world resulting in decisive legislations being enacted to combat it. This study is necessitated by the subtle nature of workplace bullying, the resultant economic loss and the psychological trauma on academic staff of Olabisi Onabanjo University.

The International Labour Organisation (ILO), the foremost international agency in the establishment of universal standard work practices does not expressly mention workplace bullying under the declaration of fundamental principles and rights at work (1998); hence the reason for its persistence especially in the academia. A study by Hoel and Cooper (2011) indicates that the effect of bullying to include lower levels of job satisfaction, psychosomatic symptoms and physical illnesses, possible expulsion from the labour market, higher absenteeism, decreased commitment and productivity, higher turnover and intent to quit. As a form of affective relationship conflict, bullying has negative effects on job performance.

An increasing amount of literature and legislation on the subject of workplace bullying and harassment has been well pronounced and written in European countries, Africa, Asia, America and Tanzania, but little has been written in the Nigeria educational sector under which Olabisi Onabanjo University belongs. Therefore, this study examined workplace bullying and harassment and its attendant effect on job performance among academic staff of OOU, Ago-Iwoye, Ogun State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The General objective of the study was to investigate the effect of workplace bullying and harassment on employee performance of Academic Staff in OOU, Ogun State. The specific objectives of the study were to:

- i. examine the effect of workplace environment on performance of Academic Staff in OOU;
- ii. examine the effect of leadership style on workplace bullying and harassment of Academic Staff in OOU;
- iii. investigate the effect of job design on workplace bullying and harassment on performance of Academic Staff in OOU; and
- iv. investigate the effect of supervisor support on workplace bullying and harassment on performance of Academic Staff in OOU.

Study Hypotheses

H0₁: Workplace Environment does not significantly affect workplace bullying and harassment of Academic Staff in OOU.

H0₂: Leadership style does not significantly affect workplace bullying and harassment of Academic Staff in OOU.

H0₃: There is no significant relationship between job design and workplace bullying and harassment on performance of Academic Staff in OOU.

H0₄: There is no significant relationship between supervisor support on workplace bullying and harassment on performance of Academic Staff in OOU.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Under this section, review was done using the following indicators for measuring workplace bullying and harassment work environment, Supervisor Support, Job Design and Leadership Style.

Conceptual Review

Bullying

Bullying is defined as repeated, persistent, continuous behaviour as opposed to a single negative act and is generally associated with a power imbalance between the victim and perpetrator, where the victim feels inferior (Oade (2019). Bullying should not be confused with tough management styles. It is negative and persistent abuse. Workplace bullying is defined as the repeated mistreatment of one employee who is targeted by one or more employees with a malicious mix of humiliation, intimidation and sabotage of performance (Margaret, 2017). The following are examples of workplace bullying behaviours: social isolation (silent treatment), rumours, personal attack of a person's private life and/or personal attributes, excessive or unjustified criticism, over-monitoring of work, verbal aggression, withholding information, withholding job responsibility, trivial fault finding, replacing proper work with demeaning jobs and setting unrealistic goals or deadline (Rowell, 2015).

Types of Workplace Bullying

Bullying happens at all levels and isn't limited to managers targeting staff. It can exist between colleagues, and staff can also engage collectively in bullying their manager, or clients and customers. Organisational downsizing and economic and job uncertainty can cause stress that can bring out undesirable interpersonal communication styles. Several types of bullying have been identified (Lentz, 2019).

- a. **Institutional Bullying:** Institutional bullying or corporate bullying is when an organisation's norms, culture or practice allow: behaviour which causes offence or undue stress to others without concern for the consequences or their wellbeing work structures, practices, policies or requirements which unreasonably burden staff without concern for their wellbeing. Work structures may lack a reasoned, justifiable or evidence-based rationale. Institutional bullying can happen in any size workplace. It may not be conscious but its consequences are often ignored or downplayed. It often happens during constrained economic times when jobs are scarce and employees have limited choices. An organisation's norms may amount to unfair practices such as impossible targets, unmanageable caseloads or unrealistic deadlines. Lack of oversight and arbitrary decisions made without consultation can have a major impact on employees' lives (Crowley & Elster, 2016).
- b. **Bullying from Managers:** A manager deliberately and repeatedly targets an employee. In the most extreme progression of events, this may come to the point where the employee feels isolated, powerless and worthless. When the employee eventually resigns, the manager finds another employee to target. This is often the most visible and well-defined type of bullying. Serial bullying is when this pattern is repeated and a manager picks on one person after another, leading to a string of resignations (Reddy, 2015). The most common form of employees bullying managers is the withdrawal of cooperation or communication. It's estimated that 15 per cent of all bullying falls into this category and is often a response to institutional bullying. Individual employees can also behave in a bullying manner to managers (Aryanne, 2019).

- c. **Bullying by Colleagues:** This is among colleagues who work at the same or similar level and includes ongoing; unwelcome comments, gestures or conduct, physical, degrading or threatening behavior abuse of power, isolation, discrimination put downs (Sutton, 2017). There are different approaches to the study of workplace bullying (Lewis & Gunn, 2017; Leymann, 2016; Salin, 2017), hence different typologies, forms and tactics of workplace have been identified. Rayner *et. al.*, (2012) suggest five categories of bullying which include threat to professional status, threat to personal standing, isolation, overwork, and destabilization. In a study of emergency service organizations in UK, Owoyemi and Sheehan (2011) identified three types of bullying namely, **personal bullying**, **administrative bullying**, and **social bullying**. Several forms have been identified in the literature such as insults, verbal abuse, excessive teasing, and aggression (Lee & Brotheridge, 2006; Rayner *et al.*, 2002; Salin, 2004). The type of bullying experienced depends to an extent on the type of task or positions of employees in the organization (Hoel & Cooper, 2007; Zapf & Einarsen, 2008).

Who is a Bully?

A bully is a person who purposely tries to hurt others by making them feel uncomfortable, hurting them by kicking, hitting, pushing, tripping, name-calling and spreading nasty rumors (Blendo, 2006). The bully hurts the other person over and over. The person being bullied feels that he or she can do nothing to stop it.

Types of Workplace Bullying

The following are; types of workplace bullies;

- a. **The Chronic Bully:** Learned childhood behavior or a personality disorder could potentially create this type of workplace bully. They are by far the most hazardous. Peter Randall⁴ believes chronic bullies do not process social information accurately and make unrealistic judgements about other people's intentions. They conceptualise themselves as being superior and powerful and are possibly not capable of empathy Christen, & Soberman, 2016).
- b. **The Opportunistic Bully:** Generally the opportunistic bully is self-centred, ambitious and prepared to win at any cost, which means controlling everything and everyone on their way to success. They seek to maximize contacts, situations and exposures to get ahead and will bully anyone they perceive as a threat. While they can exhibit similar behaviour to the chronic bully, they tend to be driven more from their own personal ambition (Adams, 2017). With strong management that expressly rejects bad behaviour towards others, they can be contained and their energy redirected.
- c. **The Situational Bully:** A person may take advantage of a workplace situation and display bullying behaviors. Workplaces that are going through organizational change, work to deadlines, have weak or dictator-style leadership and/or poorly defined hierarchies may be more at risk of situational bullying. The situational bully is likely to join the pack and become involved in 'mobbing' one or more individuals lower down the hierarchy. They will often use a chronic bully's power-base to elevate themselves to a position of importance. When the situation no longer gives opportunities for bullying, they stop (Lee & Brotheridge, 2016).

Workplace Bullying Practice

Bullying in the workplace is often associated with poor management styles and/or lack of presence of management in a department or unit. Managers need to be aware of the impact that bullying has on the staff, clients and organization. It is important to be aware of potential signs and symptoms associated with bullying in a workplace. Signs and symptoms may include:

- 1) Grievances by employees against their manager
- 2) Declining work performance of dedicated and hard-working employees

- 3) Increased stress and tensions between staff in a unit
- 4) Poor morale
- 5) Reported fear of a co-worker by other workers
- 6) Individual symptoms of depression
- 7) Increased absenteeism in a department/unit (Hutchison *et al.*, 2015; Rowell 2016)

Causes of Bullying at Workplace

Empirical investigations into the causes of bullying at work have mainly addressed in some studies. A study was by Seigne (2017) on bullying at workplace. The study found that bullying was caused by a change in the job situation for the alleged bully into a position of power. Some two out of three victims also felt that the bully was envious of them, in particular of their qualifications. BjoÈrkqvist *et al.*, (2014) content that main reasons for workplace bullying are competition concerning status and job positions, envy, and the aggressor being uncertain about his/her self. A high proportion also felt that the personality of the victim contributed to the bullying.

The victims themselves were uncertain whether or not this was the case. Another study by Vartia (2017) showed similar results that envy as an important reason for why they were being bullied, followed by a weak superior and competition for tasks or advancement or the superior's approval. Norwegian survey Einarsen *et al.*, (2016) indicated that leadership style of one's immediate superior, lack of copying resources and self-efficacy, such as low self-esteem, shyness, and lack of conflict management skills, contributed to the bullying practice.

Effects of Workplace Bullying on Employee

The effects of workplace bullying on society ought not to be underestimated in terms of employees performance. Those effects may include the loss of sections of an active labor force through resignation, early retirement or voluntary redundancy; and the cost of medical interventions for the public health system (Van, 2018). Bullying at work is not only about aggressive behavior. Bullying behavior can destroy a target's health, ability to work, emotional well-being, self-worth, and financial condition. Workplace bullies have a strong negative impact upon the business for which they work (Namie & Namie, 2013; Prentice, 2015). When a bullying atmosphere begins to pervade an organization, morale is destroyed and productivity is affected.

The workplace often contains distorted personality types that seem to have just one purpose: to find somebody else to attack, to belittle, to criticize, and to destroy (Prentice, 2015). Many leaders and managers either fail to recognize the problem or they are themselves the problem. Workplace bullying can have severe effects both for the health of those alarmed (Einarsen, 2018 & Raknes, 2019) and their job satisfaction as well as distressing organizations with high malingering, higher plan to abscond the organization, higher income and earlier retirements (Rayner, 2017). The people who face workplace aggression may have lower job satisfaction.

Workplace Bullying and Harassment and Organisational Related Outcomes

There are several previous studies on workplace bullying and organizational related outcomes. According to Lapierre, Spector and Leck, (2015), those who are obvious sufferers of workplace bullying reported highly overall job dissatisfaction. Similarly, those who bear aggression from their supervisors report high levels of job dissatisfaction (Tepper, 2018). The study showed bullying causes a decline in morale; excessive absenteeism; turnover in affected units; work team disruption; recruitment problems; an increase in worker's compensation claims, disability claims, and discrimination complaints; and employee sabotage resulting in decreased productivity profitability. Workplace bullying also leads to time wasted in problem resolution, union grievance procedures, lawsuits, and workplace violence (Namie & Namie, 2013; Needham, 2014; Prentice, 2015).

A study by Ikyanyon and Ucho (2013) found that employees who experienced low level of workplace bullying showed the highest job performance, thus confirming our first hypothesis which states that employees who perceive low level of workplace bullying will perform better on their job than those who experience high bullying in the workplace. This conforms to the finding of Einarsen *et al.*, (2014) who indicated that as a form affective relationship conflict, bullying has a negative impact on job performance. Einarsen *et al.*, (2014) however cautioned that this impact is difficult to ascertain clearly due to other factors such as absenteeism, dissatisfaction, turnover, sickness, among others (Adams, 2017).

Judge *et al.*, (2017) and Rashed (2019) who found a significant relationship between job satisfaction and job performance. It is however noteworthy that the relationship between job satisfaction and job performance has been a contentious one with some authors suggesting an insignificant relationship between the two variables (Christen *et al.*, 2016).

Indicators of Bullying and Harassment as employed in this Study

Work Environment

Characteristics of work environment include apparent and open communication which in essence addresses the employees feel that they are appropriate in the organization (Jain & Kaur, 2016). However it is necessary for staff to deliberate the organization's philosophy, mission, values and stability of Work-Life as there has to be some sort of balance between work and personal life. In general having the sense of balance will improve job satisfaction among employees (Jain & Kaur, 2016). Employees need to identify that they are being impartially rewarded and established on their performance. Impartiality means that the consequences of performance are resolute by the quantity and quality of the performance, Consistency means predictability. Subordinates want to know how their supervisor will react in a given situation. According to management studies consistency is a single most effective standard to establish with your own leadership (Jain & Kaur, 2016).

A job aid is called a repository to gain information about the work processes by the employee. According to the article written by Moore (2015), a job aid means a written tool which provides guidance to the employees in an organization. The example of job aid is such as the steps of the instruction on how to complete the appraisal form. It will help the employees get it done efficiently. The purpose of this job aid is to support the work activity (Combs, & Falletta, 2017). According to John Wiley & Sons, (2016) a job aid does not offer information until a person who gets the job aid has gained knowledge or understanding from the job aid itself. A job aid can represent a company with a self-service workplace which employees will learn on their job by themselves (Van Dam, 2015).

Job Design

The theory of job design is an important concept in business management and has been well known in the private sector for over thirty (30) years. According to (Darrah, 2015), workers are motivated by jobs in which they feel they can make a difference and jobs can be designed with that in mind. Hackman & Oldham's (2016) posited that Job Characteristic Model (JCM) is also the basis for many work design theories and extends the notion of meeting employees' human/mental needs to improve performance processes (Hackman & Oldham, 2016). They depicted positive work structure in the form of five job characteristics (skill variety, task identity, task significance, autonomy, feedback) which promoted higher intrinsic psychological factors (meaningfulness, responsibility, knowledge of results) without employee bullying and thus improve employee motivation.

Based on these theoretical underpinnings, job design methodology has been developed for and by larger organizations to handle the challenges associated with employing a large number of people in a wide variety of capacities. Among features of the modern workplace that come out of the job design model

are flextime, job-sharing, job rotation and the compressed workweek. All of these can lead to more autonomy for the worker and thereby tend to increase employee engagement (Day & Devlin, 2016).

Supervisor Support

A supervisor is the force behind the relationship of employees which they need to be attached together (Mayer & Herscovitch, 2016). The purpose of having the framework is to see the commitment of the supervisor toward the employees. Mentoring needs to be done by the supervisors in order to create a mutual understanding and relationship in between the supervisor and the employees. By having this mutual understanding, it will create a mutual satisfaction between them (Allen et al., 2015). A supervisor is also known as a person with experience, , a person who can solve problems and also the role model in the first level of organizational management (Nijman, 2014).

According to Rabey (2017) a supervisor should be a trainer to the employees as the trainer will assist the employees in getting their job done by guiding the employees on the operational process especially when it comes to a new operational procedure. The absence of supervisor support results to work related bullying. According to Tumbur and Vardi (2019), work related bullying includes giving unachievable tasks, impossible deadlines, unmanageable workloads, meaningless tasks, withholding information, deliberately or supplying unclear information, threats about job security and scapegoating.

Leadership Styles

Leadership is commonly seen as an important variable affecting organizational performance (Northouse, 2016). There are different kinds of leadership styles: autocratic, democratic and laissez faire. These types of leadership influence the leadership style of the management in an organization and the level of employee performance (Nwagbara, 2015). The quality of leadership also influences the employee performance and can result in workplace bullying Thus poor or good leadership will influence the level of employee performance of an organization and will determine the extent to which employees will be exposed to workplace bullying (Tumbur and Vardi, 2019). According to Nwagbara (2015) without shared leadership organizations will not experience high level of employee involvement. According to Gill (2016), shared leadership is characterized by the quality of interactions rather than hierarchical levels, team problem solving, conversation rather than instruction, shared values and beliefs and honesty and a desire for the common good.

Shared leadership is about collaborative, participatory leadership that takes employees' views and interests on board in decision-making and leadership process (Kotter, 2018). Employee involvement is a workplace approach designed to ensure that employees are committed to their organization's goals and values, motivated to contribute to organizational success and are able at the same time to enhance their own sense of well-being (Kotter, 2018). Thus, he argues that if the interests and opinions of employees are not considered in organizational decision-making process and leadership, they will feel disenchanted as well as alienated from the organization's leadership which will eventually lead to low employee involvement.

Ineffective leadership paves the way for workplace bullying (Namie, 2003). Frequently workplace bullies are ineffective in their own jobs and survive by stealing the ideas of another (Middleton, 2015) and taking credit for coworkers' contributions. Research by Needham, (2016) shows that workplace bullies are best able to develop and reinforce their behavior in organizations that use hierarchy for power and status, use length of service as opposed to performance as a success marker, or use reverse upward positional attainment as opposed to goal achievement. Einarsen and Raknes (2017) showed the occurrence of bullying correlated significantly with several aspects of the organizational and social work environment, particularly leadership, role conflict, and work control.

Academic Staff Performance

Burke (2015) defines employee performance as the ability to handle its internal and external functioning and relationships. This includes improved interpersonal and group processes, more effective communication, and enhanced ability to cope with organizational problems of all kinds. It also involves more effective decision processes, more appropriate, efficiency and effectiveness, economic use of resources, transparency, productivity, improved skill in dealing with destructive conflict, as well as developing improved levels of trust and cooperation among organizational members (Burke, 2015). These objectives stem from a value system based on an optimistic view of the nature of man that man in a supportive environment is capable of achieving higher levels of development and accomplishment. Essential to organization development and effectiveness is the scientific method inquiry, a rigorous search for causes, experimental testing of hypotheses, and review of results.

Chong (2018) posits that performance management is about improving performance at the individual, group, and organization levels. It is about improving the organization's ability to effectively respond to changes in its external environment, and it's about increasing internal capabilities by ensuring the organizational structures, human resources systems, job designs, communication systems, and leadership and managerial processes fully harness human motivation and help people function to their full potential. Academic staff performance is the most important dependent variables in an industrial and organizational psychology. Some main application need to be applied as to improve the work environment (Borman, 2015). Employee performance according to Sinha (2017) is dependent on the willingness and also the openness of the employees themselves in doing their job in a conducive work environment. Sinha (2017) stated that by having employee willingness and openness in doing their job, it could increase the employees' productivity and minimize incidents of workplace bullying which in turn leads to improved organizational performance.

Global perspective of Workplace Bullying

Globally, workplace bullying is a growing phenomenon which affects millions of employees. Employers should be motivated to reduce bullying as employee engagement is associated with higher profits, higher self-rated performance, and greater organizational citizenship (Medlin & Green, 2017; Barbara, & Martin, 2019). Research into workplace bullying has progressed from academic research on the phenomenon as a workplace problem into the realm of a micro-societal problem that government, employers, human resource practitioners, non-governmental bodies; voluntary or non-profit-making organizations all ought to be concerned (Bockerman and Ilmakunnas, 2015). Thus, the social problem has moved beyond the organizational level to a societal level and should be of concern to employers and government at large.

Workplace Bullying and Harassment in Finland

In Finland research, communication and practical work to address workplace bullying began in early 1990s. An article which was based on Heinz Leymann's studies and writings in Sweden and writings was published in the biggest Finnish newspaper in June 1989. It aroused a lot of interest and discussion, and many people who themselves were exposed to systematic negative treatment in their workplace, said that they got a word for their experience. During the past twenty years research has been carried out e.g. on the prevalence on bullying, antecedents and consequences of bullying, as well as measures adopted in organizations to counteract bullying at work.

Trade unions are strong in Finland, and trade union representatives (shop stewards) and particularly safety and health representatives are active players in all health and safety issues, including activities to tackle workplace bullying and harassment. According to the Occupational Health Care Act, the employer has to arrange occupational health care services for all employees. Also occupational health care personnel, particularly occupational health psychologists, take part in activities for the prevention

of workplace bullying. They give support and advice for line-managers on how to investigate and resolve cases, support those who perceive themselves as targets of bullying, and sometimes also those accused of bullying.

Most organizations in Finland carry regularly out work environment/work atmosphere surveys. In these surveys, a variety of psychosocial work environment factors/risks are assessed. Nowadays some organizations include also assessment of exposure to negative acts and bullying as well as observed/witnessed bullying in the workplace in their work atmosphere surveys. In the Work and Health Survey by the Finnish Institute of Occupational Health, the prevalence of workplace bullying has been assessed every third year since 1997. In the survey, bullying is defined Psychological violence and bullying at work means negative, oppressing and insulting treatment that is continuous and repetitive and then the respondent is asked if he or she is exposed to this kind of negative behavior at the present moment or if he or she has been exposed to this kind of negative behavior before (Vartia, 2010).

Workplace Bullying in United Kingdom

Interest in and awareness of the issue of workplace bullying emerged in the UK in the early 1990s. Through a series of radio-programmes the journalist and broadcaster Andrea Adams, who is believed to have originally coined the term workplace bullying, explored the problem and its significance in UK workplaces. The programmes and the following media debate functioned as an eye-opener for a wider audience and, with the landmark publication of the book *Bullying at work: How to confront it and overcome it* (Adams, 1992), the interest in the issue quickly gained momentum.

Within a time-span of less than ten years, the phenomenon of bullying found a resonance with large sections of the British public. Supported by empirical evidence (e.g. Hoel, Cooper and Faragher, 2001; UNISON, 1997, Quine 1999), suggesting that a substantial proportion of the UK working population perceived themselves to be bullied, with implications for individuals, organisations and society alike, the issue gradually moved upwards on the agenda of trade unions, organisations within the private and the public sectors, as well as within Governmental agencies.

In terms of prevalence, although methodologies by which evidence has been obtained vary, most studies have reported figures in the order of 10-20%. For example, Hoel and Cooper (2000) in a random nationwide survey involving 70 organisations with altogether more than one million employees found that 10.6% of respondents reported themselves to be bullied. Whilst a study in a large multinational organisation reported that 15% considered themselves bullied (Cowie et al., 2000), other studies carried out with trade union members have often reported even higher figures, with a recent study of members of the largest UK public-sector union reporting a figure of 34% (UNISON, 2009).

Workplace Bullying and Harassment in Germany

Workplace bullying has engaged Germany for 20 years now. The discussion about this phenomenon was primarily initiated by a book written by Heinz Leymann and published in 1993: *Mobbing. Psycho-terror is Arbeitsplatz und wie man sich dagegen wehren kann* (Bullying. Psycho-terror in the workplace and how you can defend yourself against it). Since the publication of this book a lot has happened in Germany. Nevertheless, the summary is only from meagre to moderate. In many companies bullying is still a word that is not talked about. Other companies, on the other hand, have responded to the challenges and are following the way of best practice. Overall successes are rather anecdotal; all in all, the balance is rather sobering. German legislature has so far failed to confront the bullying problem. Those looking for clear legislation in Germany won't find it there.

There is no single definition of what exactly is meant by workplace bullying in Germany. Also, there is no statutory legal definition. Workplace bullying can roughly be described as workplace

psychological terror because with this description much is expressed by what constitutes the workplace bullying: a steadily over a long period of time developing process with many diverse activities, which can make those affected sick and can cost them their professional and private life. And because it is precisely these aspects that make up the bullying phenomenon, they are inevitably included in the various definitions.

Workplace Bullying and Harassment in South Korea

Recently, Korean society has been shocked by the news of numerous suicides among middle or high school students who were mobbed at their schools. In addition to the violence of mobbing, bullying, and harassment at schools, this kind of violence in the workplace is an alarming concern for Korean society. For instance, there were two brutal incidents in 2012, one in February, when a man shot his former colleagues and superiors with a shotgun, the other in August, when a man robbed innocent citizens of their lives by stabbing them, though his original targets were his former colleagues and bosses. The common denominator of these two incidents is that the two men insisted they were bullied at their workplaces and their offenses were to get their revenge on the colleagues who bullied them.

Human beings are social animals, so we cannot live without other humans. People need socialization, and we have to keep in harmony with others at our organizations, such as schools or places of work. While Koreans have realized the severity of bullying and harassment problems in our society, our efforts to address the issue have focused on the bullying or harassment among students and not at the workplace. Hence, neither the Korean Statistical Information Service nor the Ministry of Employment and Labor have provided nationwide statistics or data on workplace bullying and harassment. Instead, even though the results are unofficial, some online job websites are regularly surveying and providing the relevant data in regards to bullying or mobbing in the workplace.

Workplace Bullying in Japan

Workplace bullying has been exposed much more as a social problem in recent years in Japan. It shall be explained in detail later, but if we look at a breakdown of labour counseling at prefectural Labour Bureaux, 6,627 (5.8%) of these cases were bullying and harassment in FY2002, but in FY2012 it had rapidly increased to 51,670 cases (17.0%), becoming the most common consultation for the first time.¹ And in courts and labour tribunals, cases related to workplace bullying are on the rise. Psychological injuries including suicide due to workplace bullying, which are determined as industrial accidents, are also increasing. In response to this situation, the Government has started taking countermeasures.

In Japan, there have ever been only two large scale nationwide surveys of employees regarding workplace bullying. One was conducted by the All-Japan Prefectural and Municipal Workers Union (JICHIRO) in 2010, the 100,000 Persons Power Harassment Survey (hereinafter JICHIRO Survey).³ Another was conducted in 2012 by MHLW, Workplace Power Harassment Survey (employee survey) (hereinafter MHLW Survey). This section provides an overview of the current situation with regard to workplace bullying in Japan, based on mainly these two surveys results.

Workplace Bullying and Harassment in Canada

At first glance a picture of the understanding and efforts to address workplace bullying in Canada seems to emerge in a disconnected way. However upon closer exploration a good deal is happening across the country, although there remains a sense of separateness with respect to legislation and policies nationwide. With so much attention on research into the dynamics and health harming behaviours of workplace bullying globally, in order to understand the Canadian landscape with respect to this topic, we need to understand something of the geographical, historical, and demographic trends.

The Canadian Safety Council has reported that 75% of victims of bullying leave their jobs and that workplace bullying is four times more common than sexual harassment or workplace discrimination. This implies significant monetary and human costs. Given the growing evidence that bullying represents by far the most prevalent form of violence and harassment, an emphasis in financial terms on bullying is, therefore, justifiable. Economic or monetary costs are incurred directly through loss of wages and added expenditures, primarily of health care and medical treatment.

Along with loss of wages due to sickness and absence, there are premature retirement and replacement costs in connection with high turnover (recruitment and training). Grievance and litigation and associated compensation costs, damage to equipment and production or productivity resulting from errors and accidents are also costly; with reduced performance and productivity (lack of added value to product and service) as well as loss of public goodwill and reputation. Human costs refers to the pain, fear and general reduction in quality of life for both the targeted individual as well as potential grief experienced by family and closest friends. Jacqueline Power, an assistant professor of management at the University of Windsor's Odette School of Business, has spent years researching bullies in the workplace. She says 40 per cent of Canadians have experienced one or more acts of workplace bullying at least once a week for the last six months.

Local Perspective of Workplace Bullying

Quite often, most Human Resource representatives in Africa including Nigeria fail to respond appropriately to allegations of workplace bullying and sexual harassment (Oluwakemi and Oyelere, 2017). The consequences of workplace bullying and harassment could result in increased absenteeism, decreased productivity, staff depression and a negative overall impact on bottom-line. Bullying and general harassment are far more prevalent than other destructive behaviors covered by legislation, such as sexual harassment and racial discrimination (Bockerman and Ilmakunnas, 2018).

Unlike sexual harassment, which names a specific problem and is now recognized in law of many countries (including Nigeria), workplace bullying is still being established as a relevant social problem. Employers struggle with early recognition of employees who are at risk of bullying through the inappropriate application of performance management strategies from those difficult employees who do not comply with reasonable requests or meet performance measures. Hence this study aimed at establishing the relationship between workplace bullying and performance management.

Theoretical Review

Theoretical frameworks are explanations about a phenomenon (Marriam, 2001) and provide the researcher with the lens to view the world.

Theory of Work Adjustment

This is referred to as the Person–Environment Fit or Correspondence Theory. It was originally developed by René Davis, George England and Lloyd Lofquist from the University of Minnesota in 1964. The more closely a person's abilities (skills, knowledge, experience, attitude, behaviour) correspond with the requirements of the role or the organization, the more likely it is that they will perform the job well and be perceived as satisfactory by the employer. Similarly, the more closely the reinforcers (rewards) of the role or organisation correspond to the values that a person seeks to satisfy through their work, the more likely it is that the person will perceive the job as satisfying.

The six key values that individuals seek to satisfy are achievement, conditions that encourage accomplishment and progress, comfort, the conditions that encourage lack of stress status, conditions that provide recognition and prestige, and conditions that foster harmony and service to others, safety

conditions that establish predictability and stability and autonomy the conditions that increase personal control and initiative.

Active adjustment by the individual involves them trying to change their working environment. They may seek to change the content of the job, and therefore its behaviour requirements, to better reflect their abilities. Alternatively, they may try to alter the reinforcements of the job by seeking to gain different rewards, e.g. better working conditions or greater variety or responsibility. Active adjustment by the environment may involve trying to change the person's abilities through training or trying to change their values or expectations in some way. (René *et al.* 2014). The theory relates to work environment on employee performance.

Two-Factor Theory

The Two-Factor Theory advanced by Frederick Herzberg (1959) addresses the issue of workplace motivation. The theory introduces two elements or “factors” to account for overall job satisfaction: motivators and hygiene factors. While the presence of motivators in a job can contribute to the increase in the level of satisfaction, the absence of hygiene factors in the workplace can be the cause of dissatisfaction. Hygiene factors allude to the environment and the context of the work. This can include salary, and safe working conditions. Motivators are related to the characteristics of the job itself. According to the theory motivators and hygiene factors are non-exclusive.

According to Davies (2018), satisfaction and dissatisfaction cannot be considered as the opposite ends of one continuum. Therefore an increase in the level of job satisfaction does not necessarily imply a decrease in job dissatisfaction, since the elements affecting satisfaction and dissatisfaction are different. The Two-Factor is also often referred to as the Motivation-Hygiene Theory. Herzberg (1986) adds that motivation comes from the job itself. Therefore, it is important for managers to look into the nature of the jobs they ask their employees to do.

The Two Factor Theory has had a considerable amount of practical as well as theoretical influences. In fact, from a practical perspective, the influence of Herzberg's motivation theory can be seen at every organizational level as well as within every department. From a theoretical perspective, Herzberg's motivation theory can be perceived as having similarities to Maslow's Theory of Need with the exception that for Herzberg's theory, the needs aren't placed in a progressive continuum, rather they are divided into two independent factors. In fact, Herzberg would argue that the opposite of satisfaction is not dissatisfaction since different stimuli are involved in generating each of those emotional states, reinforcing the fact that they are not on the same continuum.

The Theory of Leadership Style

Over time, a number of theories of leadership have been proposed. Most leadership theories focus on three perspectives: leadership as a process or relationship, leadership as a combination of traits or personality characteristics, or leadership as certain behaviors or as leadership skills (Northouse, 2016). Since 1980s, the transformational leadership approach has grown in public and researchers study more about it. Also, transformation means a process that change and transforms thus transformational leadership transforms individuals through emotions, values, ethics, standards and long term goals (Northouse, 2016). Transformational leadership theory was introduced by Burns (2018) and further expanded and refined by Bernard Bass (1985). Bass (2017) introduced Full Range of Leadership (FRL) Model including transformational, transactional and laissez-faire leadership (Northouse, 2014).

Apaydin (2012) argued that leadership plays an important role in allowing bullying to emerge in the work environment. Indeed, leaders have the power to influence followers to be vulnerable to being bullied by signaling what is (in) appropriate conduct (Aquino, 2019). He argues that leaders who

encourage a positive work environment, and more specifically, by communicating what is appropriate and ethical behavior, should be able to reduce bullying. Ethical leaders have a positive influence on employees' pro-social behavior and ethical conduct (Brown et al., 2015). Such ethical behavior has been shown to enhance moral reasoning which, in turn, affects the extent that employees are a target of morally questionable work situations.

Empirical Review of Literature

Work Environment

Empirical evidence has shown that bullying behavior is correlated with many features of the work environment, including organizational problems, role and functional conflicts, workloads, high stress, organizational restructuring, low satisfaction with leadership, conflicts in general in the work unit, and difficulties in discussing problems within the working group (Väänänen, 2016). Environmental factors and characteristics of the target and the bully are assumed to contribute to the onset of a bullying situation (Väänänen, 2016). Existing research has demonstrated strong links between the work environment and the prevalence of workplace bullying. For example, leadership style, job design, organizational norms and values, and communication climate have been found to have significant effects on the prevalence of bullying (Hoel & Cooper, 2015, Zapf, 2016). Still, bullying is typically seen as an 'irrational' behavior, due for example to unwanted personality traits or dissatisfaction in the workplace.

A study on workplace bullying by the Business Research Lab (2018) showed that 40% of 418 respondents reported that they had experienced bullying and 59% observed someone else being bullied in the workplace. There was also strong evidence that those identified as targets of workplace bullying were less psychologically well than others, showing significantly higher levels of anxiety and depression. Many more of those targeted by a bully appeared to be alienated from their environment and showed a greater propensity to leave their jobs (Rigby, 2019). Some places and situations are more conducive to bullying than others.

A harsh, malicious, or harmful worker would not survive in a healthy organization. "People, for social, environmental, and biological reasons, need to dominate others and the workplace provides them with a location that, if not properly managed, allows them to exercise their need to control" (Harvey, 2016). A concern is that bullying appears to be tolerated and, is therefore, becoming embedded in many organizational cultures. Yandrick, (2019) noted bullying "is a problem that knows no geographic boundaries and is not confined to a particular industry".

Supervisor Support

Reports on workplace bullying have clearly shown the key players in the bullying process to be colleagues and supervisors or managers as well as subordinates (Chartered Institute of Personnel Development, CIPD, 2016; Rayner, *et al.*, 2018). The Chartered Institute of Personnel Development (2014) reported that there are two main positions most likely to be accused of bullying across different sectors, the line managers and the peer colleagues. That is, there is a general belief that bullies are more likely to be supervisors or managers or colleagues. However in some cases, there are instances of junior employees bullying their superiors.

Research evidence has also proved that women are more bullied than men. Such report according to Hoel and Cooper (2015) is perhaps because women are more likely to report being bullied than are men, and especially if it comes from someone below them. There is always the resistance to women leaders within an organization, especially from men who are their subordinates (Sheehan, 2016). Thus, it is

important to take into consideration the role that gender plays in workplace bullying, in particular because men are less likely to report being bullied than are women (Hoel, 2015).

Job Design

Work redesign first got its start in the 1960s. Up until then the prevailing attitude was that jobs should be simplified in order to maximize employee performance (Darrah, 2017). However it was found that when subjected to highly routinized and repetitive tasks the benefits of simplification sometimes disappeared due to worker dissatisfaction in response to employee bullying due to unfriendly job design (Darrah, 2017). It was proposed that jobs should be enriched in ways that boosted motivation and engagement instead of just simplified to a string of repetitive tasks.

A study conducted by Grant, Fried, Tina and Juliet (2016) showed that a job design has sufficient role in employee engagement and performance in Fast Moving Consumer Goods (FMCG) industry of Pakistan. In a collectivist society like Pakistan people do prefer jobs with significance and autonomy. Job autonomy referring to the degree any worker has liberty to plan his or her tasks, take decisions according to the situation and find out all those means to achieve their work objectives.

Pinder (2018), in his studies done in United states noted that , the design of jobs with appropriate job characteristics has been hampered by non-compliance with the effective human resource practices and procedures in the organizations. This has accounted for the failure of most organizations in meeting up to their expected targets following employee's disengagement.

Grant, (2018) in his study in United Kingdom (UK) noted that public service employees often lack opportunities to see the impact of their jobs, how their efforts make a difference in others people's lives. He said employees in public service jobs perform tasks that are critical to protecting and promoting the welfare of individuals, groups, communities and societies. However their commitment and engagement is often limited by a lack of connection to the difference that their work makes in other people's lives.

Kahya (2017), in his study in Turkey, argued that Environmental conditions in an organization range from ordinary to extreme conditions in terms of the factors such as heat, humidity, noise, smell, light and dust. Unpleasant environmental conditions have both direct and indirect effects on employee job performance which results in organizations outcomes. The concentration to tasks of an employee who exposes to these impacts decreases, which leads to low employee performance including productivity, quality, emotional stress, and in turn causes high cost.

Leadership Style

Leadership is the art of creating a working atmosphere to achieve high performance levels and organizational goals (Manase, 2016). In fact creating such an atmosphere depends on whether the organization has a healthy structure or not. The creation of healthy organizations relates to its managers (Sergiovanni, 2016). In the other words, leaders who have a deeper awareness about workplace bullying will provide healthy working environment for their employees (Georgakopoulos, 2016).

Transformational leadership style is characterized in the Full Range of Leadership (FRL) model by four dimensions. Which include idealized influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual simulation and individualized consideration and they are referred to as the 'four I's' (Northouse, 2017). Idealized influence (charisma) is a behavior that arouses strong follower emotions and identification with the leader. Through such behavior, leaders become role models for their followers and are admired, respected and trusted (Northouse, 2017). Inspirational motivation includes behaviors that motivates and inspires followers by communicating high expectations and expressing purposes in simple ways which provides meaning and challenge to their followers work (Northouse, 2017).

Transactional leadership emerging from this model include management-by-exception and contingent reward. In fact Management by Exception (MBE) takes two forms: active and passive. Active MBE occurs when the leader monitors followers' performance, deviation from standards and rules and taking corrective action in anticipation of irregularities. Passive MBE occurs when a leader waits passively for mistakes to occur, intervening only if standards are not met. On the other hand contingent reward involves an interaction between the leader and the follower in which the leader uses rewards, promises and praise to motivate followers to achieve performance levels agreed by both parties (Northouse, 2017).

Laissez-faire or "hands-off" was identified by Bass and Avolio (2017) in the FRL model as a non-transactional factor. Laissez-faire also describes leaders who delay decision-making, give no feedback and make little effort to help followers satisfy their needs or to help them grow (Northouse, 2016). Such leaders avoid accepting responsibilities; they are absent when they are needed and take no action even when problems become chronic. Laissez-faire leaders are inactive and indicate the absence of leadership and are on the contrary to the active forms of transformational leadership. These leaders make negative effects on subordinate performance (Bass, 2017).

Academic Staff Performance

As for the effects on the organization, research has indicated consistently that bullying may lead to lower employee commitment to work and higher levels of labour turnover in organizations (Djurkovic, McCormack & Casmir, 2016). That is why researchers such as Hoel and Cooper (2014), Kivimaki *et al.* (2015) and Sheehan (2016) have all emphasized that organizations that do not pay much attention to these negative acts are at the risk of reporting reduced productivity and performance, and increased labour turnover and absenteeism within the workforce, all of which can have a negative effect on the financial base of any organization (Hoel *et al.*, 2018).

Although some German researchers have described bullying as 'foul game' in organizations (Neuberger, 1999), as 'personnel work with other means' (Zapf & Warth, 2017) or as a 'rent seeking strategy' (Kräkel, 2017), this perspective has gained little attention in the current bullying debate (Zapf & Einarsen, 2018). However, there are situations where it might be individually 'rational' or rewarding to bully somebody. For example, if the potential victim is considered either as a burden for the department or as a personal rival (Kräkel, 2017). Furthermore, studies have shown a correlation between performance-based reward systems and workplace bullying (Sutela & Lehto, 2018). It is thus possible to argue that bullying may be closely related to the phenomenon of organizational politics, that is, the phenomenon when individuals or groups deliberately act in a way that will protect or enhance their own self-interests, when their actions may or may not be in the best interest of other individuals, groups or the organizations to which the actor belongs (Kacmar and Ferris, 2020).

METHODOLOGY

This chapter discusses the research methodology that was used, in an attempt to achieve the objectives of the study. Attention was focused on research design, target population, sample size, sampling techniques, data collection instruments, data collection and analysis.

Research Design

Research design is the conceptual structure within which the research is conducted (Kothari, 2017). It is a plan showing how the study is going to be conducted. This study employed descriptive design which focuses on the event and processes of bullying and harassment behavior practice and employees

performance. The descriptive study involves descriptive analysis, interpretation, contract classification and integration of findings (Chambua, 2017).

Additionally, the design is adopted because it provides against bias and maximizes reliability of the research study (Kothari, 2017). The descriptive (survey) design was adopted for the study. The choice of descriptive research design was premised on its value and feasibility in addressing the research problem raised in the study. Its applicability for collecting standardised data allowed the researcher to create information for precisely answering the how, who, what, where and when questions concerning the measurement and determinants of workplace bullying and harassment and employees performance.

Population of the Study

Population is a group of individuals who have one or more common characteristics that are of interest to the researcher (Best & Khan, 2008). In supporting the above view, Babbie (2012) defines target population as a population which researcher is interested in gaining information and drawing conclusion. The target population under this study were academic staff of OOU, Ogun State. The total population of academic staff of OOU was six hundred and twenty eight (628).

Study Area

The study was conducted at Olabisi Onabanjo University. The reason for the researchers to select this area of study was because of the prevalence of workplace bullying and harassment as observed by the researchers.

Sample Size and Sample Size Determination

The sample frame comprises a list of all the elements in the population from which the sample was drawn while sample is a subset of the population under investigation. That is a proportion of the population selected in a systematic way so that the elements or characteristics of the population can be inferred from the findings. A truly representative sample is the one whose characteristics are approximately the same as that of the population under study. In this study, the sampling frame for this study is drawn from academic staff of OOU using an online sample size calculator from Krejcie and Morgan (1970) sample size distribution table at 95% confidence level and 0.05 error margins. Thus, a sample size of Two Hundred and Forty Three (243) was obtained.

Sampling Techniques

Triangulation method was adopted for the sampling. This includes multi-stage sampling which comprises: non-probability sampling technique (purposive) and probability sampling technique (stratified and simple random sampling techniques) were adopted for this study. This method is appropriate because it helps to obtain satisfactory representation of various subgroups within a population.

At the *first stage*, a non-probability sampling technique, purposive sampling technique, is employed in the selecting of the institution (OOU). The *second stage* is stratified random sampling technique which is used and appropriate to ensure adequacy and equal representation of the sample. The population would be divided into homogenous sub-groups, then the *third stage*, a simple random sample would be taken. The core characteristic of a randomised procedure is that every academic staff in OOU has an equal chance of being selected.

The simple random system is used to compliment the stratified sampling to select samples from each Faculty (stratum) and the number of academic staff selected from a particular level is proportional to the stratum's share of the total population. The combination of the methods will significantly help the researcher to: (a) amplify statistical representation; (b) ensure adequacy of data for analysing the various

sub populations or strata; and (c) enables the usage of different research methods and procedures for different strata.

Sources of Data

The study considers the sources on which to base and confirm their research and findings. The sources adopted primary data and secondary sources and the use of both, which was termed triangulation, or dual methodology. The primary data was collected through the use of quantitative (questionnaires); while the secondary data focused on the use already existed data extracted from previous research, articles, journals, web information, historical data and information, etc.

Research Instrument

The researcher made use of a structured questionnaire for the purpose of data collection; this was used in gathering opinions of academic staff towards fulfilling the objectives of the study. The use of questionnaire was used to collect quantitative data on the assessment of workplace bullying and harassment and employees performance among Academic staff of OOU. Participants were requested to respond to items in a self-administered, quick-answer, structured (close-ended) and unstructured (open-ended) copies of questionnaire. Primary data were collected using questionnaire.

The questionnaire comprised of two sections, the demographics of the participants and the section regarding the antecedents of workplace bullying and harassment and employees performance. Workplace environment was measured using items adapted from studies of Mowday (1979); Becker, Randal and Riegel (1995) and Wanous (1974). Some items related to leadership style was adapted from the questionnaire used by Weissenberg and Gruenfeld (1968); while job design was measured by 5 items adapted from the works of Agarwala (1978), Hoppock (1935); Kanungo (1979). Supervisor support on workplace bullying and harassment was measured by items adapted from the questionnaire of Rabinowitz (1981), Rabinowitz and Hall, (1977), and Rabinowitz and Hall (1981). The study would adopt items from previous studies (Locke, 1976; Rabinowitz, 1985; Batlis, 1978; Brief and Aldag, 1975; Gberville, 2008; Adeniji, 2011) who successfully used survey to measure the variables under study.

All the items was measured using 5 Point Likert Scale ranged from strongly disagreed (1) to strongly agreed (5). The questionnaire is shown in Appendix A. The structured questionnaire was adopted mainly to enhance uniformity of response bearing in mind that the degree of variations in behaviour is likely to be high when dealing with such complex constructs like nature of work environment, job design, supervisors support and leadership strategy. This combination of methods is well suited for obtaining in-depth responses, especially for providing broad insight into the nature of their workplace bullying and harassment and with emphasis on the performance of employees.

Validity and Reliability of the Instrument

Warwick and Linninger (2015) described the goal of research instrument as being able to obtain information relevant to the purpose of the study; to collect information with maximal reliability and validity. Consequently, content validity was adopted to authenticate that the research instrument actually measures exactly what they were designed to measure. The content validity ensures the items are certified valid by the supervisors and consultants who were experts in this field of study. Also, to ensure the reliability of the instrument, a pilot study was conducted by administering ten percent (10%) of the instruments to the respondents. This allowed for proper review and modification of the instruments before the final administration.

Therefore, in determining the reliability of this research instrument, the Cronbach's Alpha was used to measure the reliability of the instrument taking into consideration the rule of Cronbach's Alpha, which

states that the result was reliable when the research instrument yields a figure higher than 0.7. This is presented in the table below:

Table 3.1: Reliability Coefficients for the Variables in the Study

S/N	Variables	No of Items	Cronbach's Alpha (Decision Rule)	Cronbach's Alpha Results
1.	Work Environment	5	> 0.7	0.84
2.	Job Design	5	> 0.7	0.76
3.	Supervisors support	5	> 0.7	0.78
4.	Leadership Style	5	> 0.7	0.73
5.	Employee Performance	5	> 0.7	0.85

Source: SPSS Output, (2022)

A high value of Cronbach's alpha test indicates that the stability, dependability and predictability of the measuring instrument is very certain (Asika, 1991). The literature reveals that acceptable reliability should fall between 0.70 and above is desirable as recommended by (Nunnally & Berstein, 1994 & Pallant, 2007). The result of the reliability analysis sum up in Table 3.1 above revealed a high internal consistency and reliability with Cronbach's alpha values higher than the minimum perimeter, (Cronbach's alpha > 0.70). Thus, the internal consistency of the measure used in this study is considered acceptable.

Method of Data Analysis

Data analysis is not an end itself. Its purpose is to produce information that helps to address or answer the research questions of the study. The data generated for this study were analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The returned questionnaires were sorted and collated to check and minimise errors. Once the errors were checked and reduced, the questionnaires with incomplete information were discarded while completed ones were coded for analysis and inputted into SPSS Version 26.0. The descriptive statistics was based on frequencies, means and standard deviations while inferential method were used in measuring the formulated hypotheses through the use of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26.0, regression and correlation analysis were used in testing the stated hypotheses of the study.

DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Table: 4.1 Socio-Demographic Characteristic of Respondents

Variables	Categories	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Sex	Male	71	47.3
	Female	79	52.7
		150	100
Status of Staff	Associate Professor	9	6.0
	Professor	7	4.7
	Senior lecturer	26	17.3
	Lecturer 1	56	37.3
	Lecturer 2	52	34.7
		150	100
Years of Experience	0-10 years	74	49.3
	11-20 years	63	42.0
	21 years and above	13	8.6
		150	100
Highest Educational Qualification	Master's Degree	25	16.7
	Ph.D.	125	82.7
		150	100
Gross Annual Income/Pay	#2,000,000 and below	84	56.0
	# 2,001,000 and above	66	44.0
		150	100

Source: Field Survey, (2022)

Testing of Hypotheses with Correlation Analysis

Hypothesis One

HO₁: Workplace environment does not significantly affect performance of Academic Staff in OOU.

Table 4.3a: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.847 ^a	.718	.717	.846

a. Predictors: (Constant), Workplace Environment

Table 4.2a above revealed that there is a nexus at $R = .847$ between workplace environment and performance of academic staff. An examination of the table shows that the R square = .718 which implies that workplace environment accounts for only 71.8% of variations in academic staff performance; thus, it is apparent that Workplace environment has a significant effect on the academic staff performance.

Table 4.3b: ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	695.463	1	695.463	971.378	.000 ^b
	Residual	273.495	382	.716		
	Total	968.958	383			

a. Dependent Variable: Academic Staff Performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), Workplace Environment

Table 4.3b reflected that the F-value is the Mean Square Regression (695.463) divided by the Mean Square Residual (0.716), yielding $F=971.378$. The model in this table shows that the effect of workplace environment is statistically significant at (Sig =.000) and it affects the performance of Academic Staff.

Table 4.3c: Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error			
1	(Constant)	.247	.097		2.549	.011
	Workplace Environment	1.950	.063	.847	31.167	.000

a. **Dependent Variable:** Academic Staff Performance

Table 4.3c presents result of regression analysis on the effect of workplace environment on Academic Staff Performance. The result on the table reveals that workplace environment significantly affected academic staff performance with $\beta = .847$, t statistic of 31.167 and computed p-value of 0.000 which is below the level of significance (0.05) adopted for this study. The table reflects that unit change or variation in the spread of workplace environment leads to an increased effect on academic staff performance with 0.84.7 percent ($\beta = .847$).

More so, the Table revealed that the workplace environment contribute 85% ($R^2= 0.847$, p-value <0.05) effect on the performance of academic staff. Based on this result, the null hypothesis which holds Workplace environment does not significantly affect performance of Academic Staff in OOU was hereby rejected. Result of the hypothesis reflected that the workplace environment has huge and adverse effect on the performance of academic staff.

Hypothesis Two

HO₂: Leadership style does not significantly affect workplace bullying and harassment of Academic Staff in OOU.

Tables 4.3d, 4.3e, 4.3f: Results of Linear Regression Analysis on the on Academic Staff Performance

Table 4.3d: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.967 ^a	.935	.934	.337

a. Predictors: (Constant), Leadership Style

Table 4 above showed that there is a correlation at $R = .967$ between leadership style and bullying of academic staff. An examination of the table revealed that the R square = .935 which connotes that leadership style accounts for only 93.5% of variations. Thus, there is positive and significant effect of leadership style on bullying of academic staff in OOU.

Table 4.3e: ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	401.911	4	100.478	883.431	.000 ^b
	Residual	27.865	245	.114		
	Total	429.776	249			

a. Dependent Variable: Bullying of Academic Staff

b. Predictors: (Constant), Leadership Styles

Table 4.3e showed that the F-value is the Mean Square Regression (100.478) divided by the Mean Square Residual (0.883), yielding $F=883.431$. The model in this table showed that the independent variables which are leadership styles and bullying of academic staff of OOU.

Table 4.2f: Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant) Leadership Styles	-.079	.068		-1.156	.249

a. **Dependent Variable:** Academic Staff Bullying and Harassment

Table 4.2f presented result of regression analysis on leadership style and bullying of academic staff. The result from the table revealed that the independent variables which is workplace bullying harassment and using leadership style significantly affected the performance of academic staff with $\beta = .344, .772, .174$ and $.376$ respectively, t statistic of 2.998, 9.323, 2.883, 3.568 and computed p -value of 0.003, 0.000, 0.004, and 0.000, all of which are below the level of significance (0.05) adopted for this study.

The table reflected that unit change or variation in leadership style leads to an increased effect on bullying of academic staff with 0.34.4, 0.77.2, 0.17.4 and 0.37.6 percent ($\beta = .344, .772, .174$ and $.376$) respectively. Again, on leadership style as a component and indicator of workplace bullying ($R^2=0.935$, p -value <0.05) effect on performance of academic staff. Based on these results, the null hypothesis was rejected because evidence from the tables presented that leadership style significantly affect workplace bullying and harassment of Academic Staff in OOU.

Hypothesis Three

HO₃: There is no significant relationship between job design and workplace bullying and harassment on performance of Academic Staff in OOU.

Table 4.2g: Bi-Correlations table showing the relationship between job design as an indicator of workplace bullying and harassment and Performance of Academic Staff

		job design	Performance of Academic Staff
Job Design	Pearson Correlation	1	.943**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	252	252
employee performance	Pearson Correlation	.943**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	150	150

Source: Field Survey, (2022)

From the correlation table above, it was observed that Pearson Correlation method was adopted. This item shows the correlation result of the hypothesis. The Pearson value of $0.943 > 0.5$ depicts that job design significantly affects performance of academic staff in OOU. This implies that there is significant and positive relationship hence the null hypothesis was rejected while the alternative hypothesis stating that there is a significant relationship between job design and workplace bullying and harassment on performance of Academic Staff in OOU. The result of hypothesis one showed that based on the result of the tested hypothesis, it was concluded that job design as an indicator of workplace bullying and harassment has a significant relationship with the performance of academic staff.

Hypothesis Four

HO₄: There is no significant relationship between supervisor support on workplace bullying and harassment on performance of Academic Staff in OOU.

Table 4.2h: Bi-Correlations table showing the relationship between supervisor support as an indicator of workplace bullying and harassment and Performance of Academic Staff

		Supervisor Support	Performance of Academic Staff
Supervisor Support	Pearson Correlation	1	.844**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	150	150
Performance of Academic Staff	Pearson Correlation	.844**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	150	150

Source: Field Survey, (2022)

The correlation table above showed the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Analysis which aims to investigate whether there is a significant relationship between Supervisor Support and Performance of Academic Staff. The r-value of $0.844 > 0.5$ showed that there was a strong relationship between both variables hence the null hypothesis was rejected while the alternative hypothesis stating that there is a relationship between Supervisor Support and Performance of Academic Staff was accepted.

Discussion of Findings

This study examined workplace bullying and harassment and performance of academic staff in OOU. Four specific objectives were examined in this study.

The first objective which sought to examine the effect of workplace environment on performance of Academic Staff in OOU; findings revealed that workplace environment positively and significantly affect academic staff performance' and can create an avenue bullying; finding obtained from this study agree with the position of Väänänen (2016) whose finding revealed that environmental factors and characteristics of the target and the bully are assumed to contribute to the onset of a bullying situation; the finding also align with the submission of Rigby (2019) which opined that majority of those targeted by a bully appeared to be alienated from their environment and showed a greater propensity to leave their jobs; this tells the part and contribution of the environment on workplace bullying and harassment.

For the second objective which sought to examine the effect of leadership style on workplace bullying and harassment of Academic Staff in OOU; finding from this study is in agreement with the study of Middleton-Moz & Zadawski, (2014) whose finding revealed that leadership style is a strong contributory factor to bullying and harassment in the workplace; and this play out when leaders feign ignorance and walk away feeling the bullying behavior is none of their business. Finding from this study also agree with the position of Sergioivanni, (2016); whose finding presented that creating a healthy workplace has a relationship with the style of leadership in place in such organisation. Lastly; finding from this study also align with the submission of Georgakopoulos (2016) whose finding exposed hat leaders who have a deeper awareness about workplace bullying will provide healthy working environment for their employees; this statement validated the hypothesis which states that leadership style contributes to workplace bullying and harassment.

For the third objective which was hinged on exploring the effect of job design on workplace bullying and harassment on performance of Academic Staff in OOU, finding revealed that job design can significantly contribute to workplace bullying and harassment; this submission is in line with the submission of Pfeffer, (2014) which expressed that depending on how managers make decisions about job design on workplace bullying, it can be a liability or a potential source of competitive advantage for organizations. Finding also agree with the position of Pinder (2018), in his studies done in United States which noted that the design of jobs without appropriate job characteristics has been hampered by non-compliance with the effective human resource practices and procedures in the organizations; as an element and component of workplace bullying; this has accounted for the failure of most organisations in meeting up to their expected targets following employee's disengagement.

The final objective which sought to investigate the effect of supervisor support on workplace bullying and harassment on performance of Academic Staff in OOU; finding from the study exposed that supervisory support plays dominant roles in the bullying and harassment activities in the workplace and this submission validated the position of (Chartered Institute of Personnel Development, (CIPD, 2016) whose study revealed that there are two main positions most likely to be accused of bullying across different sectors, the line managers and the peer colleagues; finding also support the submission of Rayner, (2018) whose study found out that there is a general belief that bullies are more likely to be supervisors or managers or colleagues.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

It was discovered that there was close relationship between workplace bullying practice and performance of academic staff in OOU. Most academic staff were forced to take orders and work against their will and overtime are not catered for; in case of any. Based on above conclusion, workplace bullying is a harmful problem leading shortage of man power in education sector in Nigeria. Additionally, organizations incur damage such as decrease of performance, employee lack of morale, and monetary costs due to this explored the problem of workplace bullying from a theoretical perspective.

Workplace bullying is common in most organizations today especially with the presence of a diverse workforce in many organizations. In developing countries like Nigeria, it is common for employees to experience bullying at work on a daily basis. Irrespective of the form or dimension, bullying negatively affects employee well-being and performance at work and must be discouraged in order to achieve organizational effectiveness. Academic staff remains the cornerstone of every institution that wants to succeed, hence the need to provide a conducive work environment for them coupled with right leadership and design jobs in line with sociality and creation of a supportive supervisory process.

Recommendations

According to the findings of the study, the following were recommendations by the researchers:

- i. Reviewing the Human Resources structure and leadership especially at regional and district level.
- ii. Conducting regular training, workshops and seminars to train academic staff on the effect of workplace bullying to the development of education.
- iii. Developing a framework for an external expert panel to investigate serious allegations of bullying and harassment among academic staff.
- iv. Introducing new employee awards to acknowledge the contribution of employees in the categories of innovation, excellence, living the values, and difficult teaching and learning environment.
- v. Developing a new learning and development programme to embed leadership behaviors.
- vi. Developing a new culture programme covering constructive behaviors, building personal resilience and developing a capability for self-awareness and self-actualization.

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